

Effect of Supplementing Different Levels of Water Extract Anise (*Pimpinella anisum* L.) on Broiler Performance and Physiological and Digestive Organ Size and Immunity Chickens

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Abstract

This study was conducted at the College of Agriculture, University of Karbala, to study the effect of using different concentrations of anise aqueous extract to drinking water on the productive, physiological and immune characteristics of broiler chickens. Four treatments were used, with three replicates for each treatment (10 chicks for each replicate). The first treatment was free of additions (control treatment), while the second, third and fourth treatments included (5, 10 and 15 ml of anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water, respectively). The experiment lasted for five weeks and the productive traits were measured, including body weight, weight gain, feed consumption and feed conversion weekly. At the end of the experiment, before and after slaughtering the experimental birds, they were all weighed and the relative weights of the main and secondary parts and the relative lengths of the small intestine and its parts were measured. The cellular immunity of the chicks was measured. The results of the statistical analysis showed a significant improvement ($p \leq 0.05$) for the experimental treatments T2, T3 and T4 compared to the control treatment T1 in the measurements studied, while we did not find significant differences between the treatments T2 and T3. While there was a significant superiority ($p \leq 0.05$) for the treatment T4 over all experimental treatments. The statistical analysis also showed a significant improvement in the cellular immunity of the experimental treatments compared to the control treatment.

Keywords: *Anise, Broiler chickens, Chick growth, Feed consumption, Immunity.*

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Introduction

Poultry meat is a rich source of important nutrients such as amino acids, vitamins, minerals and energy that must be available in human food. As a result of the increasing population and the worsening problem of food security, it is necessary to search for means to increase production and raise its level to keep pace with the increasing needs and requirements of the local market. Among these effective methods,

medicinal plants were used in feeding broilers, laying hens, and Japanese quail, which showed positive effects on productive, immune, and physiological characteristics due to their containing natural chemicals. Medicinal plants were used as food preservatives due to their anti-pollution properties, in addition to being antibacterial and antioxidant (Hashem and Alamri, 2010). Based on studies that used medicinal plants in poultry feed in various forms, including food additives or oil or water extracts,

with the aim of improving productive characteristics and improving the health status of birds, one of these medicinal plants is anise, which can be considered a growth stimulant for birds due to its important effect in stimulating and producing digestive juices and its effect on improving their productive status (Mostaan, 2011). Medicinal plants contain important compounds, including phenols, coniodates, flavonoids, alkaloids, proteins, and anetholes (Cowan, 1999). It has a significant impact on improving the productive qualities of birds (Chrisataki, 2011). It has benefits in stimulating the secretion of digestive enzymes in the digestive system, which leads to improving the digestion of feed and improving its absorption (Mirheydar, 2010), and is an important anti-inflammatory for the respiratory system, which works to significantly raise immunity and also as a temperature reducer during heat stress (Lee et al, 2011). Due to the lack of local studies that specialize in adding the aqueous extract to drinking water for broilers, the study aimed to use different levels of the aqueous extract of anise in drinking water to identify its effect on the productive, physiological and immune characteristics of broilers during the breeding period.

Materials and Methods

The chicks were raised in three-storey batteries, each floor measuring 1 x 2 m. The floor was divided into two sections with an area of 1 x 1 m. Each cage contained 10 broiler chicks. Using gas incubators and electric greenhouses, the

temperature was regulated using an electronic thermometer from the age of one day until the marketing age (45 days). During the entire days of raising, all the conditions for raising broiler chicks were provided, with feed and water provided freely (ad libitum). A continuous lighting system was used 24 hours a day during the first three days of the chicks' life, with one hour of darkness given throughout the days of raising, in order to accustom the chicks and prevent them from becoming disturbed and crowded when the power is cut off. Plastic feed dishes with a diameter of 40 cm were used in the first week, one dish per cage, then they were gradually replaced by the circular plastic feeders used in the breeding system. Clean water was prepared and provided in inverted plastic troughs with a capacity of 5 liters throughout the breeding period. The birds were fed three types of feed: starter feed from 1-14 days of age, second feed from 15-28 days of age, and final feed from 22 days of age until the end of the experiment at 45 days of age.

The productive quality was studied according to Al-Fayyad and Naji, (2012). The qualitative characteristics of the carcass and the anatomical characteristics of the intestines were also studied according to Al-Hayali, (2004). The statistical analysis was conducted using the SAS program, (2012) and the Duncan multinomial test, (1955).

Results and Discussion

Table (1) shows the effect of using anise aqueous extract on the weekly live body weight (g) of broiler chickens.

Table 1. Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Weekly Live Body Weight (g) of Broiler Chickens ± Standard Error

Treatments	1 st week	2 nd week	3 rd week	4 th week	5 th week
T1	1.12 ± 119.61	c 2.48 ± 322.82	d 5.44 ± 696.40	d 11.02 ± 1115.93	d 16.07 ± 1683.13
T2	0.92 ± 118.17	b 2.55 ± 343.75	c 6.02 ± 751.30	c10.89 ± 1240.38	c 15.76 ± 1885.07
T3	1.18 ± 119.82	b 2.63 ± 347.96	b5.82 ± 766.30	b11.23 ± 1270.18	b 16.40 ± 1945.43
T4	1.07 ± 121.68	a 2.42 ± 553.47	a 5.53 ± 780.66	a 11.31 ± 1308.98	a 16.50 ± 2016.80
Significant	N.S	*	*	*	*

T1 First treatment: Control treatment. T2 Second equation: 5 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T3 Third treatment: 10 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T4 Fourth treatment: 15 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. N.S indicates no significant differences between the treatment means. * Different letters within the same column indicate significant differences between the groups at the 0.05 probability level.

We note that there were no significant differences between the four treatments in the first week of the chicks' life. In the second week, treatment T4 outperformed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) over both treatments T2 and T3 and treatment T1, while there were no significant differences between treatments T2 and T3. In the third week, treatment T4 outperformed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) over all treatments T3, T2 and T1, while there were no significant differences between treatments T3 and T2, which in turn outperformed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) over treatment T1. In the fourth week, treatment T4 outperformed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) over all treatments T3, T2 and T1, which in turn outperformed significantly over treatment T1, and continued This superiority in the T4 treatment continued until the end of the experiment and even in the total weight gain.

Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Weekly Weight Gain Rate of Broiler Chickens

Table (2) shows the effect of using anise aqueous extract on the weekly weight gain rate (g) of broiler chickens. We note that there were no significant differences between the four treatments in the first week of the chicks' age. In the second week, treatment T4 significantly outperformed ($P \leq 0.05$) both treatment T2 and treatment T1, while there were no significant differences between treatments T4 and T3 on the one hand and between T3 and T2 on the other hand. In the third week, treatment T4 significantly outperformed ($P \leq 0.05$) all treatments T3, T2 and T1, while there were no significant differences between treatments T3 and T2, which in turn significantly outperformed treatment T1. In the fourth week, treatment T4 significantly outperformed ($P \leq 0.05$) all treatments T3, T2 and T1, which in turn significantly outperformed treatment T1, and this continued. Superiority in T4 treatment until the end of the experiment and even in total weight gain.

Table 2. The Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Weekly Growth Rate (g) of Broiler Chickens \pm Standard Error

Treat-ments	1 st week	2 nd week	3 rd week	4 th week	5 th week	Total
T1	0.66 \pm 78.61	1.77 \pm 202.21c	2.87 \pm 376.53c	4.04 \pm 416.58d	5.23 \pm 570.19d	14.58 \pm 1644.12d
T2	0.83 \pm 80.17	1.84 \pm 221.58b	3.02 \pm 408.53b	4.11 \pm 486.09c	5.47 \pm 649.67c	15.12 \pm 1846.04c
T3	0.75 \pm 80.82	2.01 \pm 224.14 ab	2.94 \pm 415.38b	3.95 \pm 507.84b	5.49 \pm 678.22 b	15.47 \pm 1906.40b
T4	0.62 \pm 82.68	2.13 \pm 230.79a	2.76 \pm 426.18a	4.13 \pm 526.33a	5.34 \pm 711.63a	16.06 \pm 1977.61a
Signifi- cant	N.S	*	*	*	*	*

T1 First treatment: Control treatment. T2 Second equation: 5 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T3 Third treatment: 10 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T4 Fourth treatment: 15 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. N.S indicates no significant differences between the treatment means. * Different letters within the same column indicate significant differences between the groups at the 0.05 probability level.

The superiority of the addition treatments over the control treatment in the weekly body weight rate and weight gain during the weeks of the experiment may be related to the health and physiological condition of the body of the live chicks, because anise works as an antibacterial

and antifungal and improves the function of the digestive system through the action of anise in stimulating the intestinal digestive juices through the secretion of digestive enzymes and the speed of their adhesion to the surface of the mucus layer spread to the intestinal cells, which is a

suitable environment for the growth and reproduction of microorganisms and enhancing the numbers of beneficial bacteria, thus increasing their effectiveness in digesting and absorbing nutrients and increasing their readiness, which is positively reflected in production performance (Roaa et al 2024). Also, anise contains the active compound anethole and other important compounds, including phenols, conjugates and flavonoids, which have an effective role in the significant increase in improving digestion processes and secreting digestive enzymes, thus increasing growth and improving body weight and weight gain rates (Bayram, 2007). (Elkomy et al 2023). It is consistent with (Ismail et al 2021), who found an intestinal improvement in the productive characteristics of broiler chickens when fed anise seeds and anise oil.

Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Weekly Feed Consumption Rate of Broiler Chickens

Table (3) shows the effect of using anise aqueous extract on the weekly feed consumption rate (g)

for broiler chickens. The results indicated significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) in weekly feed consumption during the experimental period, as it was found that there were no significant differences between the treatments during the first week. As for the second week, treatment T4 outperformed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) over treatment T2 and treatment T1, while there were no significant differences between treatment T4 and treatment T3 on the one hand, and between treatment T3 and treatment T2 on the other hand. This result continued in the third week as well. As for the fourth week, treatment T4 outperformed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) over treatments T1 and T2, while there were no significant differences between treatments T4 and treatment T3. Both treatments T3 and T2 outperformed the control treatment T1. As for the total feed consumption for the period (1-5 weeks), it witnessed a significant increase. ($P \leq 0.05$) for treatment T4 compared to treatments T3, T2 and T1, which in turn outperformed each other and the control treatment T1, respectively.

Table 3. The Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Weekly Feed Consumption Rate (g) for Broiler Chickens \pm Standard Error

Treat-ments	1 st week	2 nd week	3 rd week	4 th week	5 th week	Total
T1	1.17 \pm 124.99	3.15 \pm 335.67c	6.33 \pm 647.63c	7.47 \pm 762.34c	10.26 \pm 1094.76c	28.36 \pm 2965.39d
T2	1.11 \pm 126.67	3.21 \pm 361.18 b	6.45 \pm 678.16b	8.02 \pm 850.66b	11.38 \pm 1195.39b	30.19 \pm 3212.06c
T3	1.06 \pm 126.89	3.19 \pm 363.11ab	6.56 \pm 681.22ab	8.52 \pm 873.48a	11.52 \pm 1214.01a	31.34 \pm 3258.71b
T4	1.13 \pm 129.81	3.22 \pm 369.26a	6.72 \pm 686.15a	8.28 \pm 878.97a	11.44 \pm 1216.89a	30.45 \pm 3281.08a
Signifi-cant	N.S	*	*	*	*	*

T1 First treatment: Control treatment. T2 Second equation: 5 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T3 Third treatment: 10 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T4 Fourth treatment: 15 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. N.S indicates no significant differences between the treatment means. * Different letters within the same column indicate significant differences between the groups at the 0.05 probability level.

Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Feed Conversion Efficiency of Broilers

Table (4) indicates the effect of using anise aqueous extract on the feed conversion efficiency of broilers, as no significant differences were observed in the feed conversion efficiency between treatments in the first week of the chicks' age. In the second week, treatment T4 outperformed significantly

($P \leq 0.05$) the control treatment T1, while there were no significant differences between treatments T2, T3, and T4 on the one hand, and between T1, T2, and T3 on the other hand. In the third week, treatment T4 outperformed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) both T1 and T2, while there were no significant differences between T4 and T3 on the one hand, and between T3 and T2 on the other hand, and both treatments T3 and T2 outperformed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) the

control treatment T1. In the fourth week, treatment T4 outperformed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) all treatments. T1, T2 and T3, while there were no significant differences between treatments T3 and T2, which were significantly superior ($P \leq 0.05$) to the control treatment T1. In the fifth week, treatment T4 was significantly superior ($P \leq 0.05$) to all treatments T3, T2 and T1, which were superior to each other,

respectively. As for the feed conversion efficiency rate of birds throughout the experiment, significant differences appeared between the treatments, as treatment T4 was significantly superior ($P \leq 0.05$) to all treatments T1, T2 and T3, while there were no significant differences between treatments T3 and T2, which were significantly superior ($P \leq 0.05$) to the control treatment T1.

Table 4. Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on Feed Conversion Efficiency (g feed/g weight gain) for Broiler Chickens \pm Standard Error

Treatments	1 st week	2 nd week	3 rd week	4 th week	5 th week	Total
T1	0.01 \pm 1.59	0.02 \pm 1.66b	0.03 \pm 1.72c	0.02 \pm 1.83c	0.03 \pm 1.92d	0.02 \pm 1.80c
T2	0.02 \pm 1.58	0.02 \pm 1.63ab	0.02 \pm 1.66b	0.01 \pm 1.75b	0.02 \pm 1.84c	0.02 \pm 1.74b
T3	0.03 \pm 1.57	0.01 \pm 1.62ab	0.02 \pm 1.64ab	0.02 \pm 1.72b	0.02 \pm 1.79b	0.01 \pm 1.71b
T4	0.02 \pm 1.57	0.03 \pm 1.60a	0.01 \pm 1.61a	0.01 \pm 1.67a	0.02 \pm 1.71a	0.02 \pm 1.66a
Significant	N.S	*	*	*	*	*

T1 First treatment: Control treatment. T2 Second equation: 5 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T3 Third treatment: 10 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T4 Fourth treatment: 15 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. N.S indicates no significant differences between the treatment means. * Different letters within the same column indicate significant differences between the groups at the 0.05 probability level.

The significant improvement in body weight and weight gain rate of the addition treatments during the weeks of the experiment, shown in the tables above, is due to the fact that anise has a growth-enhancing role with an important effect stimulating digestion and improving the absorption coefficient of nutrients, and the presence of the two active compounds anethol and eugonol, which are important and effective elements in the stimulating role of digestion (Cabuk et al., 2003). Also, the anise plant contains good proportions of the nutrients necessary for the healthy growth of the body, as it contains protein, fatty acids, amino acids, calcium, vitamin B and iron. These important nutrients and their presence in the extract explain the extent to which the body benefits from them, which improves the average body weight as a final stage, and thus is reflected in improving the utilization of the digestion products of nutrients (Lanshout, 2000). It also has a role in improving the resistance of pathogenic microorganisms in the digestive system, which affects the improvement of the level of utilization of the feed materials consumed, which is reflected in the positive effect on the live weight of birds.

As for the improvement in the feed conversion factor for the addition coefficients, the anise extract works to positively stimulate the digestive tract to increase the digestibility of protein and cellulose (Jamroz and Kamel, 2002) and this is positively reflected in converting them to body growth, increase and weight. The researcher (Hernandez, and his colleagues 2004) proved that the aqueous extract of the aromatic plant has an effective effect in positively improving digestion in the digestive tract and effectively in increasing the enzymes lipase, amylase and pancreas, and thus increasing the digestion of starch and fats and increasing the absorption of nutrients (due to the length of the intestinal villi) and the representation of nutrients into meat production (Bayram, and his colleagues, 2007). This, in turn, has an effective effect on stimulating the digestive tract to increase the benefit from the feed consumed and increase weight and thus improve the feed conversion factor. It agrees with (Ismail et al 2021) found an intestinal improvement in the productive characteristics of broilers when fed on seeds Anise and anise oil.

Effect of Using the Aqueous Extract of Leaves on the Mortality Rate and the Production Index of Broilers

Table (5) shows the effect of using the aqueous extract of leaves on the mortality rate and the production index of broilers, as it is noted that the mortality rate decreased significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) in all treatments of adding the aqueous extract compared to the control treatment T1, which recorded the highest mortality rate significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to the treatment T4, which had the lowest mortality rate compared to the rest of the treatments T2 T3, which did not have significant differences and in which the mortality rate decreased significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to the control treatment T1.

The same table shows a significant superiority ($P \leq 0.05$) in the production index of treatment T4 over all treatments T3, T2 and T1, which were significantly superior ($P \leq 0.05$) to each other, respectively, i.e. T3 over T2 and T2 over treatment T1.

Table 5. Effect of Using aqueous Extract of Leaves on Mortality Rate (%) and Production Index of Broiler Chickens

Treatments	Mortality ratio %	Productive index
T1	a 0.54 ± 6.66	d 2.36 ± 249.84
T2	b 0.26 ± 3.33	c 2.47 ± 299.38
T3	b 0.23 ± 3.33	b 2.55 ± 314.38
T4	c 0.14 ± 1.67	a 2.66 ± 341.47
Significant	*	*

T1 First treatment: Control treatment. T2 Second equation: 5 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T3 Third treatment: 10 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T4 Fourth treatment: 15 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. N.S indicates no significant differences between the treatment means. * Different letters within the same column indicate significant differences between the groups at the 0.05 probability level.

From the results of Table (5), it is clear that the mortality rate increased significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) in the control treatment compared to the treatments in which the leaf extract was used, and in all proportions, the decrease in the mortality rate is an important economic characteristic in raising broiler chickens, and all

treatments of adding the leaf extract led to a decrease, and this is due to the role and importance of the leaves in health and enhancing it and increasing the tolerance and resistance of birds to stress factors, and adding the extract with drinking water reduces mortality by improving the immune characteristics of the bird, and considering the extract an antioxidant as it protects the cell membrane from damage by free radicals and also being an anti-viral and anti-microbial, thus it can improve general health, which is reflected in the immune response of the bird and thus increasing its resistance to diseases and reducing the mortality rate, as the improvement of the health status is attributed to the role of the active compounds contained in olive leaves. As for the production index, it is clear from the table that there are significant differences in the production index values of broiler chickens between the treatments of adding the extract to drinking water and the control treatment. The improvement in the production performance characteristics is positively reflected in the production index values. The reason for this improvement in the production index and performance scale in treatment T4 is attributed to the increase in the average live body weight and the vital ratio in addition to the improvement in the feed conversion efficiency, as the production index scale is directly proportional to the average live body weight and the vital ratio. Thus, the production index scale increases in treatment T4 compared to the rest of the treatments T3 and T2, which in turn outperformed the control treatment T1. The positive changes that occurred in the improvement in the production performance of the birds that consumed the extract and their superiority over the control treatment can be attributed to the components present in the extract, including phenols and flavonoids, the most important of which is Oleuropein, which is of great importance and is considered helpful in getting rid of pathogenic microorganisms. This result is consistent with what Wenk (2002) stated that the increase in performance associated with the presence of supplements of Plant-based materials with poultry feed mainly due to their polyphenolic content, Polyphenolic compounds help in

eliminating pathogenic microorganisms that are likely to spread in the digestive system of these animals.

Effect of Using Aqueous Extract of Anise Plant on the Relative Weight of the Main Cuts of Broiler Carcasses

Table (6) shows the effect of using anise aqueous extract on the relative weight of the main cuts (breast, drumstick and thigh) of broiler carcasses. The results showed a significant superiority ($P \leq 0.05$) in the treatments of adding

the extract T4, treatment T3 and treatment T2 compared to the control treatment T1, as treatment T4 was significantly superior ($P \leq 0.05$) in the three main cuts (breast, drumstick and thigh) over all treatments T3, T2 and T1, which in turn were significantly superior ($P \leq 0.05$) to each other, respectively, as T3 was significantly superior ($P \leq 0.05$) to T2 and T1, and T2 was significantly superior ($P \leq 0.05$) to T1 for all main cuts (breast, drumstick and thigh). Thigh for broiler carcasses.

Table 6. The Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Relative Weight of the Main Cuts (%) of Broiler Carcasses \pm Standard Error

Treatments	Brest relative weight	Relative weight of thigh	Relative weight of the ankle-femoral junction
T1	0.28 \pm 25.71d	0.16 \pm 15.30d	0.12 \pm 12.27d
T2	0.24 \pm 26.02c	0.14 \pm 15.54c	0.11 \pm 12.33c
T3	0.23 \pm 26.27b	0.15 \pm 15.71b	0.09 \pm 12.65b
T4	0.25 \pm 26.44a	0.13 \pm 15.90a	0.10 \pm 12.83a
Significant	*	*	*

T1 First treatment: Control treatment. T2 Second equation: 5 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T3 Third treatment: 10 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T4 Fourth treatment: 15 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. N.S indicates no significant differences between the treatment means. * Different letters within the same column indicate significant differences between the groups at the 0.05 probability level.

Table (7) indicates that adding anise aqueous extract contributed to improving the weight ratios of the main cuts of the broiler carcass, and the weight gain ratio increased with the increase in the percentage of adding the aqueous extract, and the increase in the weights of the main cuts (breast, drumstick and thigh) is a good indicator of the quality of the broiler carcasses produced, because most of the meat is found in the main cuts of the broiler carcass (Al-Fayyad and Naji, 1989). The significant increase in the average live body weight (Table 1) and weight gain (Table 2) and the significant improvement in feed conversion efficiency (Table 3) for all treatments of adding anise aqueous extract compared to the control treatment was reflected in the relative weight of the main carcass cuts, as the significant increase ($P \leq 0.05$) in the relative weight of the main cuts was a reflection of the increase in body weight resulting from food metabolism and vital interactions in the body (Al-Hamo, 2003). This result was consistent with what was reported by Naji and Al-Fayyad (1989), where they showed the existence of a direct relationship between the

average body weight and the percentage of dressing on the one hand and the percentage of the main cuts of the carcass on the other hand. The relative increase in the weight of the main cuts can be attributed to the role of the extract in supporting the building of muscle tissue and increasing protein deposition in body tissues and building muscles in the chest, thigh and femoral junction by helping to stimulate the thyroid gland to secrete the hormone thyroxine, which supports the building of muscle tissue and affects protein synthesis (Topalovic, 2015).

Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Relative Weight of Secondary Cuts of Broiler Carcasses

Table (7) shows the effect of using anise aqueous extract on the relative weight of secondary cuts (back, wings and neck) of broiler carcasses, as we notice significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) between treatments, as the control treatment T1 significantly outperformed ($P \leq 0.05$) all addition treatments T2, T3 and T4, which in turn significantly outperformed each other ($P \leq 0.05$)

in the relative weight of secondary cuts (back, wings and neck), as T2 significantly outperformed ($P \leq 0.05$) T3 and T4, and T3 significantly outperformed ($P \leq 0.05$) T4 and all secondary cuts (back, wings and neck) of broiler carcasses in the experiment. The significant decrease in the relative weight of secondary cuts may be attributed to For the carcasses of the addition treatments, the significant increase in the relative weights of the main cuts of the

addition treatments is positively reflected in the significant decrease in the relative weight of the secondary cuts and vice versa. Abu Taleb (2008) indicated that there was a significant increase in the rates of the main cuts of the carcasses of Japanese quail chicks with a significant decrease in the relative weight of the secondary cuts of the carcass when feeding the quail chicks on anise seeds compared to the control.

Table 7. The Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Relative Weight of Secondary Cuts (%) of Broiler Carcasses \pm Standard Error

Treatments	Relative weight of back	Relative weight of wings	Relative weight of neck
T1	0.26 \pm 27.35a	0.12 \pm 13.06a	0.06 \pm 6.30a
T2	0.23 \pm 27.03b	0.10 \pm 12.77b	0.04 \pm 6.09b
T3	0.22 \pm 26.78c	0.08 \pm 12.63c	0.05 \pm 5.94c
T4	0.23 \pm 26.64d	0.09 \pm 12.49d	0.03 \pm 5.68d
Significant	*	*	*

T1 First treatment: Control treatment. T2 Second equation: 5 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T3 Third treatment: 10 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T4 Fourth treatment: 15 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. N.S indicates no significant differences between the treatment means. * Different letters within the same column indicate significant differences between the groups at the 0.05 probability level.

Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Relative Weight of Small Intestine and Caecum Parts of broiler Chickens

Table (8) indicates the effect of using anise aqueous extract on the relative weight of small intestine and caecum parts of broiler chickens, as it is noted that there is a significant superiority in the relative weight of each of the small intestine,

duodenum, jejunum, ileum and caecum in all treatments of adding the aqueous extract compared to the control treatment, as treatment T4 significantly outperformed ($P \leq 0.05$) all treatments T3, T2 and T1, which in turn significantly outperformed each other ($P \leq 0.05$) respectively, as T3 significantly outperformed ($P \leq 0.05$) T2 and T1, and T2 significantly outperformed ($P \leq 0.05$) T1.

Table 8. The Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Relative Weight of the Small Intestine and Cecum (%) of Broiler Chickens \pm Standard Error

Treatments	Relative weight of small intestine	Relative weight of duodenum	Relative weight of jejunum	Relative weight of ileum	Relative weight of cecum
T1	0.036 \pm 3.53d	0.006 \pm 0.52d	0.014 \pm 1.39d	0.015 \pm 1.62d	0.007 \pm 0.47d
T2	0.033 \pm 3.97c	0.005 \pm 0.66c	0.010 \pm 1.53c	0.016 \pm 1.78c	0.003 \pm 0.59c
T3	0.035 \pm 4.32b	0.005 \pm 0.78b	0.012 \pm 1.64b	0.013 \pm 1.90b	0.005 \pm 0.70b
T4	0.030 \pm 4.84a	0.005 \pm 0.91a	0.011 \pm 1.82a	0.014 \pm 2.11a	0.004 \pm 0.81a
Significant	*	*	*	*	*

T1 First treatment: Control treatment. T2 Second equation: 5 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T3 Third treatment: 10 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T4 Fourth treatment: 15 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. N.S indicates no significant differences between the treatment means. * Different letters within the same column indicate significant differences between the groups at the 0.05 probability level.

Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Relative Length of the Small Intestine and Cecum of Broiler Carcasses

Table (9) shows the effect of using anise aqueous extract on the relative length of the small intestine and cecum of broiler carcasses, as it is noted that there is a significant superiority in the relative length of each of the small intestine, duodenum, jejunum, ileum and cecum in all

treatments of adding the aqueous extract compared to the control treatment, as treatment T4 significantly outperformed ($P \leq 0.05$) all treatments T3, T2 and T1, which in turn significantly outperformed ($P \leq 0.05$) each other, respectively, as T3 significantly outperformed ($P \leq 0.05$) over T2 and T1, and T2 significantly outperformed ($P \leq 0.05$) over T1 (control treatment).

Table 9. The Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Relative Length of the Small Intestine and Cecum (%) of Broiler Carcasses \pm Standard Error

Treatments	Relative length of small intestine	Relative length of duodenum	Relative length of jejunum	Relative length of ileum	Relative length of cecum
T1	1.11 \pm 9.41d	0.16 \pm 1.51d	0.42 \pm 3.71d	0.44 \pm 4.19d	0.08 \pm 0.78d
T2	1.17 \pm 10.05c	0.17 \pm 1.68c	0.36 \pm 3.95c	0.40 \pm 4.42c	0.12 \pm 0.98c
T3	1.05 \pm 10.44b	0.13 \pm 1.80b	0.35 \pm 4.08b	0.38 \pm 4.56b	0.09 \pm 1.10b
T4	0.96 \pm 10.82a	0.14 \pm 1.92a	0.36 \pm 4.20a	0.42 \pm 4.70a	0.07 \pm 1.21a
Significant	*	*	*	*	*

T1 First treatment: Control treatment. T2 Second equation: 5 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T3 Third treatment: 10 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T4 Fourth treatment: 15 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. N.S indicates no significant differences between the treatment means. * Different letters within the same column indicate significant differences between the groups at the 0.05 probability level.

It is noted from Tables (9) and (10) that the use of anise aqueous extract led to an increase in both the relative weight and length of the small intestine, duodenum, jejunum, ileum and caecum in the addition treatments compared to the control treatment, as the production characteristics indicated an increase in live weight and feed consumption as well as an increase in the efficiency of food conversion in the addition treatments. This increase in growth and feed consumption requires an increase in the weight and length of the small intestine and caecum to match the rapid growth and development of the body organs, including the digestive system, in order to allow more space for the digestion and absorption processes. The active ingredients in the extract also stimulated the parts of the digestive system, including the intestine and caecum, to grow and develop rapidly. The results of this study agreed with what Shafey et al. (2013a) indicated by using anise powder with feed in feeding broiler chickens and its effect on the digestive system, as there were significant differences in the

weights and lengths of the small intestine, duodenum, jejunum and ileum and their thickness for the leaf addition treatments compared to the control treatment. It also agreed with what was mentioned by Shafey et al. (b2013) that using the leaf extract (Oleuropein) with the feed provided to broiler chicks showed superiority in the weights, lengths and thickness of the small intestine, duodenum, jejunum and ileum.

Effect of Using the Aqueous Extract of Anise on the Immune Response of Broiler Chicks

Table (13) indicates the effect of using anise aqueous extract on the immune response of broiler chickens, as we notice a significant superiority ($P \leq 0.05$) in treatment T4 when compared with the other treatments T3, T2 and T1 in the cellular immunity trait (DTH), while the other treatments outperformed each other significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) respectively, as T3 outperformed significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) over T2 and T1, and T2 outperformed significantly

($P \leq 0.05$) over the control treatment. This case of significant superiority ($P \leq 0.05$) continued for the addition treatments among themselves and

over the control treatment in the Newcastle immunity trait (ELISA), the relative weight of the Fabricia gland and the Fabricia index.

Table 10. The Effect of Using Anise Aqueous Extract on the Immune Response of Broiler Chickens \pm Standard Error

Treatments	Cellular immunoassay (DTH) Newcastle	immunoassay (ELISA) Relative	weight of Fabricius gland	Fabricius index
T1	0.013 \pm 0.141d	255.9 \pm 2632.8d	0.003 \pm 0.059d	0 \pm 1.000d
T2	0.016 \pm 0.184c	241.6 \pm 2747.2c	0.003 \pm 0.088c	0.015 \pm 1.492c
T3	0.013 \pm 0.205b	217.5 \pm 2791.2b	0.002 \pm 0.100b	0.012 \pm 1.695b
T4	0.014 \pm 0.228a	236.8 \pm 2850.0a	0.002 \pm 0.117a	0.013 \pm 1.983a
Significant	*	*	*	*

T1 First treatment: Control treatment. T2 Second equation: 5 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T3 Third treatment: 10 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. T4 Fourth treatment: 15 ml anise aqueous extract per liter of drinking water. N.S indicates no significant differences between the treatment means. * Different letters within the same column indicate significant differences between the groups at the 0.05 probability level.

The significant improvement in immunity may be due to the addition of anise to aromatic plants that play an important role in their work as antioxidants, as they play an important role in raising the vitality of the body and the general health of birds, i.e. they play an important role in stimulating the immune system, increasing the level of immune globins, maintaining the membranes of lymphocytes and phagocytic cells, then increasing the bird's immune response and giving it the ability to resist infection with diseases and germs and attack them during the breeding period, especially viral diseases such as Newcastle and Camporo, which is reflected in enhancing the body's cellular and humoral immunity. It also plays an indirect role in the metabolic rate and the effectiveness of the endocrine glands (Ciftci et al 2005), (Bayram et al, 2007), (Gebreyohannes, G. and Gebreyohannes, M. 2013). It is consistent with the result of (Elkomy et al 2023), who found a significant increase in the weight of the Fabricia gland, thymus and spleen in quails. Al-Yayani.

Conclusion

This study shows that when using different additions of anise aqueous extract to drinking water on the productive, physiological and immune characteristics of broiler chickens, there was a significant improvement in the experimental treatments T2, T3 and T4

compared with the control treatment T1 in the measurements that were studied, while we did not find significant differences between the treatments T2 and T3. While there was a significant superiority of the T4 treatment over all experimental treatments, as well as a significant improvement in the cellular immunity of the experimental treatments compared with the control treatment.

References

- Abu-Taleb, A. M., Hamodi, S. J., & El-Alfifi, S. F. (2008). Effect of using some medical plants (anise, chamomile, and ginger) on productive and physiological performance for Japanese quail. *Isotope and Radiation Research*, 40(4), 953–964.
- Bayram, I., Cetingul, I. S., & Akkaya, B. (2007). Effects of anise seed (*Pimpinella anisum* L.) on egg production, quality, cholesterol levels, hatching results, and antibody values in blood of laying quails (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*). *Archiva Zootechnica*, 10, 1–5.
- Çabuk, M., Alçiçek, A., Bozkurt, M., & İmre, N. (2003). Antibacterial properties of the essential oils isolated from aromatic plants and possibilities of using them as alternative feed additives. In *II. National Animal Nutrition Congress* (pp. 184–187).

- Christaki, E. V., Bonos, E. M., & Florou-Paneri, P. C. (2011). Comparative evaluation of dietary oregano, anise, and olive leaves in laying Japanese quails. *Revista Brasileira de Ciência Avícola*, 13(2), 97–101. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1516-635X2011000200003>
- Ciftci, M., Güler, T., Dalkılıç, B., & Ertaş, O. N. (2005). The effect of anise oil (*Pimpinella anisum* L.) on broiler performance. *International Journal of Poultry Science*, 4(11), 851–855. <https://doi.org/10.3923/ijps.2005.851.855>
- Cowan, M. M. (1999). Plant products as antimicrobial agents. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*, 12(4), 564–582. <https://doi.org/10.1128/CMR.12.4.564>
- Dawood, R. J., & Al-Dalawi, R. H. (2024). The effect of adding different levels of anise seeds and oil (*Pimpinella anisum* L.) on some production parameters of Lohman chicken eggs. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1371(1), 072033. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1371/1/072033>
- Elkomy, A. E., El-Saadany, A. S., Shreif, E. Y., Bayoumi, A. A., El-Maged, A., Alagawany, M. H., Saleh, M., Cho, A. A., Kim, S., & Eltahan, H. M. (2023). Anise and grape seed oils as a feed additive to improve performance, immune response, antioxidant activity, and reduce caecal pathogenic microbes of quail. *Archives Animal Breeding*, 66(4), 379–390. <https://doi.org/10.5194/aab-66-379-2023>
- Gebreyohannes, G., & Gebreyohannes, M. (2013). Medicinal values of garlic: A review. *International Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences*, 5(9), 401–408. <https://doi.org/10.5897/IJMMS2013.0960>
- Hashem, M., & Alamri, S. (2010). Contamination of common spices in Saudi Arabia markets with potential mycotoxin-producing fungi. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 17(2), 167–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2010.02.013>
- Ismail, F. S. A., El-Sherif, K. H., Beshara, M. M., & Hafez, H. A. (2021). Effects of dietary anise oil, anise seed powder, and turmeric supplementation on the productive performance of broiler chickens. *Journal of Animal and Poultry Production*, 12(10), 323–329. <https://doi.org/10.21608/jappmu.2021.191950>
- Jamroz, D., & Kamel, C. (2002). Plant extracts enhance broiler performance. *Journal of Animal Science*, 80(Suppl. 1), 41.
- Langhout, P. (2000). New additives for broiler chickens. *World Poultry*, 16, 22–27.
- Lee, J. B., Yamagishi, C., Hayashi, K., & Hayashi, T. (2011). Antiviral and immunostimulating effects of lignin-carbohydrate-protein complexes from *Pimpinella anisum*. *Bioscience, Biotechnology, and Biochemistry*, 75(3), 459–465. <https://doi.org/10.1271/bbb.100748>
- Mirheydar, H. (2001). *Herbal information: Usage of plants in prevention and treatment of diseases*. Islamic Culture Press Center.
- Mostaan, K. H. (2011). Evaluation of two medicinal plant extracts in diets of Japanese quails. *Annals of Biological Research*, 2(6), 657–661.